

Speculation on Radiation from a Moving Charge Part III

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 20, 2021

In (1), the frequency distribution of radiation emitted from an accelerating charge is calculated. In this note, we try to argue that this classical calculation is very similar to the quantum calculation of a bound state, although in the latter case x is involved instead of t . The classical electromagnetic result is not a solution of a Schrodinger equation, nevertheless, there exists an expression for energy flux emitted proportional to $E(x,t)$ the electric field squared. (This in turn depends on $r(t)$, $v(t)$ and $a(t)$ (acceleration).) In a number of papers (e.g. (2)), it is argued that $E+iB$ is the wavefunction of a photon. For the photon ($c=1$), E and B have the same strength and are perpendicular. Thus, $E(x,t)$ carries the information of the photon wavefunction, especially in the sense of a Fourier decomposition. In a classical treatment of an accelerating charge, $E(x,t)$ is expanded in a Fourier series of $\exp(i\omega t)$, where $\exp(i\omega t)$ represents a photon of frequency ω . Thus, $E(x,t)$ is a photon distribution just as $W(x)$, the wavefunction of a bound quantum particle, is a distribution in $\exp(ikx)$. In one case, one may find a quantum object in a frequency/momentum state of ω , in the other a particle in the momentum state k . In both cases, the treatment is over all x or all time with a distribution function existing for both. For the bound particle, one has $W^*(x)W(x)$, density, and for the emitted radiation, the energy emitted as a function of time. Thus, for the quantum case, $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ and for the radiation case, $P(\omega/t) = a(\omega) \exp(i\omega t) / |E(r(t),t)|$. Furthermore, for the bound particle, $a(p)a(p)$ is the probability to have the particle in a momentum state of p regardless of position and in the radiating case, $A^*(\omega)A(\omega)$ is the probability for radiation of frequency ω to be emitted regardless of the time. Nevertheless, time is well known at each instant. In addition, "interference" is part of both the construction of $W(x)$ and $E(t)$.

Classical Radiation Emission from an Accelerating Charge

In (1), the power emitted per unit solid angle from an accelerating charge is:

$$dP(t)/d \text{ solid angle} = |A(t)| |A(t)| \text{ where } A(t) = \sqrt{c/(4*3.14)} [R E]_{\text{ret}} \quad ((1))$$

E is the electric field evaluated at a time $t-R/c$ (i.e. ret) and R is the distance from the charge to the measuring point.

$RE(t)$ is given specifically by: $\{n \times (n-v) \times dv/dt\} / \{1-v.n\}^3$ where v is really v/c and n is a unit vector pointing from the origin to the measuring point. ((2))

$$A(\omega) = 1/\sqrt{2*3.14} \text{ Integral } (-\text{infinite to infinite}) A(t) \exp(i\omega t) dt \quad ((3))$$

Thus: $d^2 I / d\omega \text{ solid angle} = 2 |A(\omega)||A(\omega)|$

In general, taking the Fourier series of a function as in ((3)) is a mathematical procedure, but in the case of radiation, $\exp(i\omega t)$ represents a physical object, namely a photon with frequency/momentum ($c=1$) of ω . $A(\omega)$ gives the weight for such a photon to be produced in an expansion of $E(r(t),t)$, the electric field, although ultimately it is $|A(\omega)||A(\omega)|$ which appears in an expression of energy radiated i.e.

$$dW / d\text{solid angle} = \text{energy emitted per solid angle} = \text{Integral } (-\text{infinite to infinite}) |A(\omega)||A(\omega)| \quad (4)$$

So far, all of these equations, taken from (1), represent classical physics except for the idea that $\exp(i\omega t)$ represents a quantum object and $E(t)$ involves interference of $\exp(i\omega t)$ (see ((3))) in order to create a function of time which ultimately represents energy emitted per time per solid angle when squared.

Photon Wavefunction

There are a number of articles in the literature which argue that $E+iB$ represents a quantum vector wavefunction of a photon and that the quantum mechanical equation of such a photon follows from Maxwell's equations with no sources i.e. $-dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$ and $dB/dt = \text{grad} \times E$. In (2), it demonstrated that one may treat the photon in a very similar manner to the Dirac equation for the electron except for the fact that matrices associated with a spin 1 object are used. The result leads to Maxwell equations with no sources.

For a radiating accelerating charge, one utilizes Maxwell's equations with a source present, but the leading E and B terms (i.e. the ones which drop as $1/R$) are of the same magnitude and perpendicular just as in the photon case. E (and also B), however, are no longer proportional to $\exp(ikx-iEt)$ ($k=E$ $c=1$), but E may be written as Fourier series of $\exp(i\omega t)$. This suggests the physical presence of a variety of photon frequencies. In other words, the Fourier series is not just a mathematical procedure, but represents physical reality, just as in the case of quantum mechanics (e.g. $\exp(ikx-iEt)$). $E(t)$ and $B(t)$ should still represent quantum physics i.e. a wavefunction, if they represent it for the photon.

The case of radiation being emitted from an accelerating charge appears at first to be a classical nonequilibrium problem. In this note, however, we wish to consider how similar this process is to a bound state quantum particle.

Radiation from an Accelerating Charge and Quantum Bound States

At first, one may point out clear differences between these two cases. Radiation from a charge represents a situation in which energy is being released per time which seems to be a nonequilibrium case. One may, however, consider the time interval $-\text{infinite to infinite}$ and note that a fixed amount of energy is released. The rate of release per time is then a probability for energy release i.e. the probability to find photons emitted at a certain time, much like $W^*(x)W(x)$ is the probability to find a quantum particle at x in the range $-\text{infinite to infinite}$. We attempt to compare the two cases in general;

1. $W^*(x)W(x)$ for a bound state (from -infinite to infinite) is similar to $dP(t)/$ solid angle. The integral of W^*W is normalized so that it is 1. The integral of $P(t)$ over time yields the amount of radiation emitted.

2. $W(x)$, the wavefunction may be decomposed into a Fourier series: $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ is not simply a mathematical function, but represents the wavefunction of a free particle with momentum p . “ $a(p)$ ” is its weight and a^*a is the probability to find a particle with momentum p . Note: a^*a has no x dependence so this is the probability to find a particle with p , i.e. $P(p)$ throughout the system even though x is well defined at each point.

$\text{Sum over } p \ a^*a = 1$.

Similar results hold for a radiating system. $dP(p)/dx = b |RE(t)| |RE(t)|$. $E(t)$ may be decomposed into a Fourier series with $\exp(iwt)$ represents physical photons : $E(t)= \text{Sum over } w \ A(w) \exp(iwt)$. $A^*(w)A(w)$ is the probability to find a photon of frequency (momentum) w in the system without focusing on a specific time. It may be noted, however, that time is well defined.

3. Interference occurs in both systems. $W^*(x)W(x)$ is the probability to find a particle at x . Given that $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$, the various $\exp(ipx)$ interfere to create the final W which in turn is used to calculate $W^*(x)W(x)$. Similarly in the radiating case, $dP(t)/d \text{ solid angle} = b |RE(t)| |RE(t)|$ is the probability to have radiation at time t . $E(t)= \text{Sum over } w \ A(w)\exp(iwt)$, so the various $\exp(iwt)$ also “interfere” to create the wavefunction $E(t)$ which is then square to produce the amount of energy radiated per time.

4. Conditional probability. For a quantum particle, $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. It seems one may construct a similar result for the radiating accelerating charge:

$$P(w/t) = A(w)\exp(iwt) / dP(t)/d\text{solid angle}$$

5. Issue of a potential. $W(x)$ may be found by solving a Schrodinger equation with a potential in the nonrelativistic case. $V(x)$ may be written as $\text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$, so it is a smoothed version of a system that delivers stochastic hits of momentum k with probability V_k . In the case of emitted radiation, matters are a little more complicated. E depends on derivatives of a source (charge density) which has a leading term $q \ v(t-R/c)/R$ and magnetic potential which is dependent also on $v(t-R/c)$. d/dt and d/dr essentially yield the same result acting on $v(t-R/c)$ leading to $a(t-R/c)$ i.e. acceleration.

Formally, (1) gives the result:

$$RE = \{nx(n-v)x \ dv/dt\} / \{1-v.n\}^3 \quad ((5))$$

Here v is really v/c and n a unit vector pointing from a fixed origin to the point of measurement. (The charge is at r_1 measured from a fixed origin and R is from r_1 to the point of measurement.)

Thus, E depends on $r(t)$, $v(t)$ and $a(t)$. $r(t)$ enters through $t-R/c$ where $R \approx r-n \cdot r_1$. " r " is the vector from the origin to the measurement point. As a result, there are sources in the radiation problem similar, but more complicated to the $V(x)$ source in the quantum particle case. One may readily take a Fourier transform of $V(x)$, but in the radiation case, one simply takes a Fourier transform of E . Thus, the picture of "interactions" due to the accelerating charge on the wavefunction E (electric field) are not so clear in the radiation case.

Thus, it seems that a quantum bound particle and radiation from an accelerating charge are both treated in a similar quantum manner.

Conclusion

In the literature (2), it is argued that $E+iB$ (E =electric field and B = magnetic field) is a quantum vector wavefunction for a photon (with the E and B linked by Maxwell's equations with no sources). The energy density $.5(\epsilon_0 E E + 1/\mu_0 B B)$ is analogous to $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is a particle wavefunction.

In this note, we try to extend these ideas to radiation emitted from an accelerating charge. In this case and the photon case, E and B are perpendicular and of the same magnitude with $c=1$. Thus, one may focus on E . Instead of using energy density $.5(\epsilon_0 E E + 1/\mu_0 B B)$, we consider $dP(t)/d$ solid angle, i.e. the amount of radiation emitted per time per solid angle. This is proportional to $|RE||RE|$ (where R is the distance from the charge to the measuring point). Thus, we take E as the wavefunction of the emitted radiation with its square giving a kind of energy emission probability density. E may be expanded in a Fourier series $E = \text{Sum over } w A(w) \exp(iwt)$ just as $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. In both cases, $\exp(iwt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ are physical. One represents a photon, the other a momentum wavefunction of a quantum particle. In both cases: dW/d solid angle = $\text{Sum over } w A^*(w)A(w)$ and $1 = \text{Sum over } p a(p)a(p)$. Thus, $a(p)a(p)$ is the probability to find the particle in momentum state p through x ranging from $-\infty$ to ∞ and $A^*(w)A(w)$, the probability to find a photon with frequency/momentum w throughout time. $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ and we argue $P(w/t) = A(w) \exp(iwt) / dP(t)/d$ solid angle.

Thus, it seems that radiation from an accelerated charge expressed as a constant times RR time the wavefunction E (electric field) squared follows the same quantum mechanical formalism as $W(x)$ for a quantum particle.

References

1. Jackson, J. . Classical Electrodynamics John Wiley and Sons 1975
2. Bialynicki-Birula I. On The Wavefunction of the Photon (Acta Physica Polonica A 1993)
<http://przyrbwn.icm.edu.pl/APP/PDF/86/a086z1p08.pdf>